

Study Case of Erizo Juan Santamaría: from free map to official cartography

Jaime Gutiérrez Alfaro

Laboratorio Experimental, Centro Académico de Alajuela, Instituto Tecnológico de Costa Rica – jgutierrez@itcr.ac.cr

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Abstract

Digital maps are a widely used tool for accessing products and services, territorial planning or distribution of resources during emergencies. Under-representation of marginalized communities is an example of historical socioeconomic exclusions reconfiguration through geospatial data. Each mapping process of a marginalized community is a learning opportunity because of its own particularities. Whether these are methodological, in terms of access to technologies, level of digital literacy or even political-administrative when the data is to be made official. This article presents with enough detail the case of mapping the urban informal settlement Erizo Juan Santamaría in Alajuela, Costa Rica. The neighborhood was an empty space on OpenStreetMap and now is part of the country's official cartography. Mapping was conducted by people who live in the community and a research group from a public university. The process was carried out using technologies based on free/open software and participatory cartography methodologies, consistent with a decolonial perspective of public university. The inclusion of Erizo Juan Santamaría in digital maps is a step forward to improve the quality of life of the inhabitants of the neighborhood through the digital space justice and represents a successful case of reclaiming the right to be represented in the map.

1. Introduction

In the mid-20th century, Latin America questioned the economic situation of the region in terms of its role in international trade exchange processes, which were detrimental to the countries producing raw materials and beneficial to the industrialized ones. Developmentalism economic theory was spread throughout the region driven by the United Nations Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean (CELAAC), promoting imports substitution processes through economic policies that boosted local industrialization. The effort sought to reduce the gaps between the so-called modern countries of the first world and the laggards of the Third World. The cities were the epicenter of the promised prosperity, the place where improvements in the quality of life, access to job opportunities and better public services were concentrated. The imminent effect was a massive internal migration from rural areas to the cities that caused a reshape of demographic patterns and economic landscapes across the region. However, the dream of the modern Latin American city was shattered during the 1970s, leaving a series of problematic social situations that turned poor migrants from rural areas into new urban poor. The Latin American city was configured as a space in which highly urbanized areas coexist with others where the reality is informality and the denial of access to basic public services. The marginalized developed their own urban planning strategies, self-managed access to public services, and defined the social norms of coexistence in neighborhoods that were invisible to official entities. Across Latin-American region, this common urban process shape the identity of the cities, nowadays with variants that are product of different trajectories until now days (Contreras Castro, 2011).

Digitization processes, driven by information and communication technologies, emerge replicating existing socioeconomic inequalities, and digital maps do not escape from that poor reflection on the historical contexts that produced the present that was being represented. Some residential areas located on the margins of historic and

commercial city centers were digitally made invisible, while mapping platforms were acquiring greater validity as the mechanism that represents reality. Given the availability of geospatial technologies, free and open sources software, open data, and participative mapping methodologies, it is imperative to focus efforts on representing marginalized communities, such as urban informal settlements. This is a contribution in reducing digital inequality and its effect on quality of life. Greater representation in digital maps impacts urban planning processes and helps strengthen resilience strategies, while understanding community space contributes to a better distribution of resources, attention to the particularities of the territory, and identification of challenges to be addressed. Making them visible contributes in improving the relationship of marginalized neighborhoods with their surroundings, whether other communities or institutional actors.

Figure 1. Aerial view of Erizo Juan Santamaría informal settlement. In the middle is located “La Plaza” (the soccer pitch), the most important social area of the community.

The case presented in this article, mapping Erizo Juan Santamaría (EJS) informal settlement in Alajuela, Costa Rica, is situated in the historical context and digital exclusion processes

just described. In 2017, Laboratorio Experimental (LabExp) a research group, in sync with the objectives of the public university to which it's associated with, set out to start developing a mapping project of a vulnerable community in the university environment. When reviewing commercial maps and OpenStreetMap, the digital marginalization of EJS became evident, as the entire neighborhood was represented as an empty space.

In the next section of this article, a big picture of EJS informal settlement is depicted. It's dynamics with surrounding neighborhoods and institutions related to the territory, also the perspectives that guide the mapping before it was conducted. It is followed by a section with details of the mapping process, pointing out three aspects: What elements were mapped? What tools were used? And what mapping activities were carried out?. Also, a focus on the key activities that help disseminate the project results and made the Municipal city Council decision to request that some elements of the map should be added into the official cartography of Costa Rica. The last section presents final remarks and insights after the mapping process.

2. Context of the mapping process

The informality of the EJS lies in the fact that people who live in the space do not own the land. The territory where the neighborhood is located belongs to two public institutions, one part to the Municipality of Alajuela and the other to the National Institute of Housing and Urbanism (INVU). The municipality is an autonomous institution whose powers reach a third level in terms of political-administrative order (a canton). Among its functions is to regulate the land use and provide public services such as clean water access, sewage treatment, garbage collection and maintenance of public infrastructure. INVU is a national level institution founded in 1954, one of its functions is “to design, coordinate and promote housing programs that allow people to have access to their own home, according to their needs and possibilities.” (Instituto Nacional de Vivienda y Urbanismo, s. f.). The territory in which EJS is located, before being occupied, was intended for the construction of recreational and sewage treatment facilities for the surrounding neighborhoods build by INVU.

Figure 2. Map of Erizo Juan Santamaría built with open data produced by the community and Laboratorio Experimental research team.

In the 1970s, the first families began to occupy the territory where the settlement is currently located. At the time, the space was an area with coffee plantations, topographically flat near the Ciruelas River bank and in the opposite direction a small hill

with a significant slope. The first people to settle in the neighborhood organized themselves to adapt the territory for housing purposes, delimit public spaces, build basic infrastructure elements and gradually gain access to some public services such as electricity and water. Since then, the community has maintained a constant strive to improve their living conditions, solving their basic common infrastructure needs, access to public services and solve their needs collectively. Today, EJS is inhabited by approximately 400 families (1200 people) in about 4 ha territory.

Both public institutions which own the land, surrounding neighborhoods and nearby businesses, have interests and opinions about the informal settlement, which are manifested in a tense coexistence that includes marginalization, manipulation, stigmatization, and invisibility. For the Municipality, EJS has been a manipulable locality for electoral purposes through broken promises of projects to improve the public infrastructure, but also with threats of violent eviction attenuated by the request of electoral support. INVU, since its foundation in the 1950s decade, had been an improving housing conditions actor in the area. Two neighborhood, that surround EJS to the east and west, called respectively INVU Las Cañas and Erizo, received INVU support for the construction. In 2016, the institution approved a program for housing provision to extremely poor families of EJS, but to date it has not materialized into changes in the place, although families keep hope. Crossing Ciruelas River, a middle class residential urbanization and Plaza Real Shopping Center are located. The neighborhoods and the shopping center share an interest to move out the inhabitants in the territory where the informal settlement is located. This interest is fueled by social stigmas associated with the people who live there and reinforced by news in tabloid press. Additionally, in the case of the shopping center, there is a special interest in continuing a road that could make it easier to access its facilities, but whose route would pass through the middle of EJS. Due to its proximity to Alajuela city center, the people who live in the informal settlement have access to health services, transportation, education, supermarkets and various shops. In recent years, the reactivation of the interurban train service has increased the interest in revaluing the territories near the train line, among which is EJS, therefore the pressure to gentrify the space also increased.

With this starting point, LabExp and EJS representatives agreed to work together on a 4-year project, funded by the public university Tecnológico de Costa Rica. The project aimed to make the informal settlement visible to decision-making institutions and surrounding neighborhoods through the map. Caminos de la Villa project was an inspiration and reference for the work to be done, as they mapped informal settlements in the city of Buenos Aires (Argentina) in order to highlight problems in infrastructure and public services (Caminos de la villa, s. f.).

LabExp, which is part of the School of Computing, has free software, open data and action-participatory research as transversal work axes. The approach to mapping of this research group is given from the free software tools used mainly in relation to the OpenStreetMap ecosystem, as well as from the experience of developing mapping workshops for children. In both cases, with undergraduate university students participating as programmers of adaptations to the required software or facilitators of activities. The work plan for the project was based on participatory mapping, free software and open data, from an ethical and decolonial positioning around the work with the community and from the public university. Mapping seen as a process that should aim at social transformation, overcoming

mere transfers of knowledge, technology or assistentialism, in the terms of Freire, articulating the work as a form of non-bank education (Freire, 2015). This mapping, therefore, must be dialogical, horizontal, and encourage critical thinking among the people who create and use the map, understanding the effect of the product generated on their quality of life. In the same sense, the appropriation of the process by the inhabitants of the EJS is in accordance with Segato's proposition of adapting the university contents to the needs of the various collective subjects, as part of her proposal for university decolonization. The result of the work should respond to the needs and be useful in the context of its effort to survive and project itself into the future (Segato, 2015).

The proposed perspective for approaching this work should not be confused with a refusal to recognize the privileged position from which the LabExp mapping team embarks on the process. This privilege includes the very fact of being academics from the public university, professors, and students whose work is compensated economically¹, with a high level of digital literacy and access to technology. It is also worth mentioning that none of the people who participated in LabExp had roots in the EJS settlement, although the process itself led us to build a relationship of friendship and solidarity with the neighborhood.

3. Mapping process

More than the final result, was the process the main goal, the community engagement and the commitment to make visible EJS in digital maps. It was necessary to identify elements to map that would make sense for the community in its relationship with decision-making institutions, the surrounding neighborhoods, and that would be useful for the people living in EJS. The mapping process was carried out with free and open tools from the OSM ecosystem: OSMTracker to capture GPS data in the field, FieldPapers to collect data in workshops and conversations with neighbors, JOSM to edit the OSM map and QGIS both to create maps to capture data and to create maps to disseminate the mapping process. The mapping activities and dynamics included: free cartography workshops with students at the local school, field trips and unstructured playful dynamics with children in the neighborhood.

While the team held meetings and had conversations to identify the most relevant elements of interest, the LabExp conducted a first mapping activity in INVU Las Cañas Primary School. 88 students participate in free cartography workshops, which were instructed by university undergrad students (see Figure 3) Concepts like local knowledge and collaborative knowledge construction, as well as basic cartography terminology, are constructed through playful activities. Cartography related tasks are completed through the use of free software OpenStreetMap and Field Papers (Gutiérrez Alfaro et al., 2018). Despite the high participation of school children, who live in the EJS, it was striking that not too much data about the settlement was obtained. A possible explanation was obtained during the workshops, when a teacher said that there was nothing more

¹ The LabExp team acknowledges that the volunteer work of people from the EJS community participating in the process should have been remunerated, as well than it was the case for people from the public university. However, the university's policies on the use of resources imposed a limitation on payment. In a later project developed with the community and financed with external funds, it was possible to financially compensate the EJS participants (Gutiérrez Alfaro et al., In press).

than “La Plaza”, the soccer pitch (view Figure 1). Evidently, that comment is another example of EJS marginalization.

Figure 3. Undergrad university student facilitating a Free Cartography Workshop in INVU Las Cañas School.

It was determined to prioritize two elements to be mapped, The first was the houses, since INVU was interested in developing a project to improve the neighborhood's housing infrastructure, the institution needed to carry out a census. Through a number in each house, the map could be linked to the census data. The second were the streets and alleys, with the intention that neighbors improve the way in which they gave their home addresses when requesting services. At all times, OpenStreetMap was considered as the repository where the collected data would be stored.

Figure 4. Mapping of houses during the INVU census.

The mapping of houses for the INVU census was developed jointly with officials from the institution, through field work. INVU's objective was to apply a socioeconomic survey to families, the data was associated with a house number that they wrote with a permanent marker on the facade of each house and kept the house record on a freehand paper map. The LabExp-EJS mapping team saw the opportunity to create a digital map with the houses and the numbers assigned by INVU, through geospatial data captured with OSMTracker, georeferenced photographs and annotations in FieldPapers. This was the first complete tour in the neighborhood, which also gave rise to some internal tensions regarding the map, specifically some neighbors expressed their desire that their houses and alleys in front of them not appear on any published map, which we respect. Also arose the need to modify OSMTracker to adapt it to the specific needs of the process. A digital map was created on the uMap platform from OSM data (Comisión ErizoJS, 2021), so that EJS residents and INVU officials could check the location of the houses and their numbers. The map is still in use EJS residents, in some cases to give precise addresses and in others to keep alive the hope that the housing project offered by INVU will become a reality.

Figure 5. Infants mapping public infrastructure with OSMTracker in an unstructured playful dynamic.

With the first version of the map ready, field trips were the mechanism to continue improving the map data. The use of satellite images was not a choice, because as reported in (Yeboah et al., 2021) for cases in Africa and Asia, the urban landscape in this informal settlement is changing rapidly and there is a high density of structures, so field mapping is more appropriate. During these visits to the neighborhood informative opportunities emerged, inhabitants were engaged in dialogue about the map, its relevance, and its uses. At the same time, these conversations served to improve elements of the map. Children were also interested in participating in the process, so unstructured playful dynamics were designed so that children could walk around the neighborhood, specifying the location of some elements of public infrastructure such as street lighting, speed bumps, or trees. For this dynamic, children were asked to use OSMTracker and preliminary versions of the EJS map in such a way that they captured data and then drew the improvements that needed to be incorporated on the map (view Figure 5). These dynamics allowed a digital literacy process to be carried out based on the specific questions of the participants.

In addition to the mapping, two activities were key to foster a feeling of ownership of the process by the residents of the neighborhood and to disseminate the partial and final results. The first was the production of short videos in order for the community's inhabitants to narrate their reality about infrastructure, show the neighborhood, and describe the relationship with the decision-making institutions, in such a way that they linked these experiences with the process of mapping. In one of the videos, Exandra, who is the president of the settlement's housing committee, explains the origins of the neighborhood and the relationship that exists with the INVU. In the video, she uses the digital map built during the census, with the location of the houses and the number assigned by the INVU. In another video, José Monterrey, president of the EJS pro-improvement committee, comments on the infrastructure projects for the neighborhood's and how the mapping project is relevant to support these intentions. Both videos were circulated through social networks, neighborhood chats, and national circulation press. With our doubt, the videos were a mechanism of appropriation of the process of constructing the maps and making EJS visible (Umaña Venegas, 2021).

Figure 6. During COVID-19 pandemic, a mechanism to keep in touch with the community and communicate news about the project was using social media.

Figure 7. Election day for deciding names of streets and alleys.

The second key activity was a participative and democratic voting process to choose names for streets and alleys mapped. During one week, residents submitted various proposals for names for the streets or alleys of their respective homes, the requirement were accordance with the ones from the National

Nomenclature Commission, because of the expectation of making the resulting names official. The names proposals were circulated among the other residents during another week. Then, the voting day was organized, simulating a real election, so that they could decide names based on the proposals presented (see Figure 7). Additionally, signage material was produced to physically demarcate the streets and avenues with their new names (see Figure 8 and 9), the design of the materials was copied from the official signage of Alajuela city. This activity foster the validity of the whole mapping process internally and externally. Some surrounding neighborhoods, express envy (in a good sense) about the EJS elected their own names and having signage in the streets.

The mapping process was completed by 2021, Erizo Juan Santamaría appeared on the digital maps. In OSM, the houses were included with their respective numbering according to the needs of the INVU, the streets and alleys with the names selected by the inhabitants, elements of public infrastructure, trees and the proper name of the neighborhood. The community was also represented on other commercial maps. Thanks to the dissemination of the short videos and press releases in the University's and national media, the mapping process of Erizo Juan Santamaría was known to the members of Municipal Council of Alajuela. The Council dedicated an entire session to hear about the project and agreed to make official the names of the streets and alleys decided in the voting process by the neighbors. In addition, the Council managed to make official the names before the National Nomenclature Commission of the National Geographic Institute.

Figure 7. Erizo Juan Santamaría inhabitants talking in Avenida La Paz (Peace Alley).

4. Final Remarks

The case presented in this article is unique in Costa Rica where, through participatory cartography, the production of free geospatial data is contributed to official cartography. The active participation of the EJS community validates the process and that was a key factor for the Municipal Council of Alajuela, where the neighborhood is located, to make official the traces and names of the streets and alleys of EJS for municipal purposes. Furthermore, at the request of the municipal council, the National Nomenclature Commission of the National Institute of Geography (IGN) approved the names at the national level. This is remarkable in terms of the relation between IGN and the OpenStreetMap community in Costa Rica, because IGN wasn't open to integrate crowdsourced data into their official geospatial database (Arriaga et al., 2023), but this case could help to make open data contributions more common.

Figure 8. View of “Alameda la Amistad” (Friendship Alley).

Both EJS and LabExp benefit from the experience. The visibility of EJS on digital maps makes it easier for the inhabitants to access services that were previously denied or restricted due to the insecurity that people offering the service felt about visiting the neighborhood, partly due to stigmatization and partly because the location led to an empty space on the digital map. Given the increasing use of digital maps to access services and make decisions, it is important to discuss the right of communities to appear on digital maps. From the point of view of LabExp, as representative of the public university, with the project was possible to engage university students from computer engineering in the development and adaptation of geospatial free software tools for the mapping process, which complements their university training and gave them a different perspective on how programming can affect the quality of life of vulnerable population (Carstens Soto & Gutiérrez Alfaro, 2021; Oviedo Sanchez et al., 2019). Together, community and LabExp, received a grant by the Uruguayan Agencia Nacional de Investigación e Innovación (ANII) that allows the group to make one step further in the usage of the data by integrating it in an application to manage the risk of social conflict caused by limitations on access to drinking water in an informal settlement. The grant allowed us to advance the design of the app, not the implementation, but the process was valuable in continuing to empower the community, on the one hand, through economic recognition for the time invested in the design and, on the other hand, by accompanying them to present the results of the work themselves through a presentation at the RightsCon 2023 conference (ErizoJSAPP Commission, 2023).

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